

O32. Phosphogypsum valorization at pilot scale: Continuous reactor design and CO₂ mineralization

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Phosphogypsum (PG), a byproduct of phosphoric acid production, presents significant environmental challenges due to decades of accumulation in large stockpiles, which can release contaminants such as phosphorus (P) and rare earth elements (REEs) [1]. The FIC-Fighters project, a European Horizon initiative, addresses these challenges by developing sustainable solutions for PG valorization through CO₂ sequestration via mineral carbonation. This process converts PG into high-value materials such as precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) and sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄), which have applications in cement production, battery manufacturing, fertilizer formulations, and the detergent industry. To achieve this, PG is treated by a soda-rich solution, which can be derived from industrial wastes such as caustic soda from the aluminum industry [2, 3].

This study focuses on optimizing a continuous reactor design for PG conversion at pilot plant scale, aiming to improve reaction efficiency and process scalability. A continuous stirred-tank reactor (CSTR) system is proposed as an alternative to traditional batch processes, offering advantages in reaction efficiency, scalability, and cost-effectiveness. Key operational parameters – including solid-to-liquid ratio, reaction temperature, residence time, and CO₂ injection rate – were systematically optimized to maximize PG conversion, process efficiency and product quality. Pre-treatment steps such as selective washing and filtration were also investigated to improve impurity removal.

Comprehensive characterization of intermediate and final products was performed using SEM-EDS, XRF, XRD, ICP, and TGA, enabling in-depth analysis of phase evolution, elemental composition, and impurity behavior throughout the process. The optimized process demonstrated high PG-to-product conversion rates, offering a scalable and sustainable valorization route suitable for industrial implementation. This work contributes to the circular economy by transforming industrial waste into marketable materials while sequestering CO₂, aligning with the EU Green Deal and broader climate-neutral objectives

Keywords: phosphogypsum, continuous reactor, CO₂ sequestration, mineral carbonation, industrial waste valorization, circular economy

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